

Phase transformation in chemically synthesized Ni nanoparticles

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Abstract

The chemically synthesized Ni nanoparticles exhibit both fcc and hcp structures which are reported to be magnetic and nonmagnetic respectively [1]. Since most of the chemical methods employ carbon-based solvents, the possibility of Ni₃C with crystal structure similar to that of hcp Ni influences the magnetic properties. However, the structure and magnetic property correlation of hcp Ni and Ni₃C are still under debate [2]. Although hcp Ni is ferromagnetic at room temperature from theoretical studies [3], most of the studies report nonmagnetic nature. We show that the nonmagnetic phase is Ni₃C which can be easily identified from the thermomagnetic analysis. The residual magnetism arises due to the presence of trace amount of fcc Ni.

Keywords: Ni₃C, HCP.

References

1. C.N. Chinnasamy et al, J. Appl. Phys. 97(2005) 10J309.
2. Lin He et al, J. Magn. Magn. Mater. 322(2010) 1991-1993.
3. X. He et al, J. Appl. Phys. 97,(2005) 106107